

The structure of the products resulting from dehydroacetic acid and hydrazines

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Abstract : Dehydroacetic acid, 3-acetyl-4-hydroxy-6-methyl-2H-pyran-2-one, a biologically active compound, undergoes a variety of reactions with alkyl, aryl and heteroarylhydrazines producing various products (pyranopyrazoles, bipyrazoles, pyrazolyl 1,3-diketones, pyrazolones, etc.) under different experimental conditions. The structure of these products has been established by employing NMR spectroscopy, mass spectrometry, theoretical calculations and X-ray crystallography.

Keywords : Dehydroacetic acid, bipyrazole, hydrazines, pyrazole.

Dehydroacetic acid (1, 3-acetyl-4-hydroxy-6-methyl-2H-pyran-2-one, DHAA), a biologically active compound, has shown to have good antibiotic and fungicidal effects¹ besides showing strong antiseptic properties². It has also been used to enhance vitamin C stability, in vegetable food processing³ and as a preservative⁴. Dehydroacetic acid, having several reactive sites, is very susceptible to attack by the nucleophilic reagents at the carbonyl of the acetyl group, carbon atom terminating the conjugated carbon chain at 6-position, the lactone carbonyl and the carbonyl of the 4-position. A study of the tautomerism of dehydroacetic acid using ¹H, ¹³C (solution and CPMAS), gated ¹H-decoupling techniques, deuterium-induced isotope effects on ¹³C chemical shifts, fully coupled C, H correlation (FUCOUP) and molecular modeling with AM1 has established that the compound exists as the 3-acetyl-4-hydroxy-6-methyl-2H-pyran-2-one in solution and also in the solid state⁵.

Dehydroacetic acid can be obtained from ethyl-acetoacetate⁶, *t*-butylacetoacetate⁷, acetyl acetic acid⁷ and α -oxo-ketone⁸. It continues to remain the most inexpensive starting material for the synthesis of a variety of compounds e.g. natural products^{9,10}, benzodiazepines¹¹⁻¹³, metal chelates of Schiff bases for biological properties such as antitumor, antibacterial and antiviral¹⁴⁻¹⁶ and a host of compounds with diverse chemical structures¹⁷⁻¹⁹. In view of growing interest in the reactions of significance available in the literature, we herein report a de-

tailed account of the structure of the products resulting from the reaction of dehydroacetic acid with alkyl, aryl and heteroarylhydrazines under various experimental conditions.

Discussion

Perkin and Bernhart²⁰ described the first reaction involving DHAA and phenylhydrazine in 1884. However, the authors failed to propose the correct structure for the product. Later, Stolle²¹ in 1905 and subsequently Benary²² in 1910 reinvestigated this reaction and isolated two products, which were characterized as 1,1'-diphenyl-3,3'-dimethyl-(4,5'-bipyrazol)-5-ol (4) and 3,6-dimethyl-1-phenylpyrano[4,3-*c*]pyrazol-4(2H)-one (3). The exclusive formation of 4 was also described under different conditions. The formation of these products were proposed via the intermediacy of phenylhydrazone of 1 (2) (Scheme 1).

Russian group²³ reported the reaction between methyl ether of 1 (5) and phenylhydrazine affording 3,6-

Scheme 1

dimethyl-2-phenylpyrano[4,3-*c*]pyrazol-4(2*H*)-one (6) as the exclusive product. They also reported that 1 reacts with phenylhydrazine hydrochloride in methanol producing 3 and 4, besides a keto ester (7) as a by-product (Scheme 2). A keto ester (7) as a by-product was shown to be methanolysed product of 3 as proved by refluxing 3 in methanolic solution containing a few drops of hydrochloric acid.

Scheme 2

The reaction of 1 with phosphorus oxychloride furnished 4-chloro-3-(1-chlorovinyl)-6-methyl-2*H*-pyran-2-one (8), which on treatment with alkyhydrazines resulted in the formation of 3 (R = CH₃, CH₂CH₂OH). However, the reaction of 8 with aryl/heteroarylhydrazines resulted in the formation of 6 which are isomeric with 3²⁴ (Scheme 3). The formation of products (3 and 6) may be explained on the basis of initial attack of more nucleophilic, substituted nitrogen of the hydrazine on the more reactive C₄

of pyrone ring of 8. It was reported that reaction of 1 with phenylhydrazine in methanol followed by refluxing in xylene in presence of *p*-toluenesulphonic acid resulted in the formation of 3 along with a compound identified as 11 (discussed later). The structure assignment was unambiguously made by homonuclear ¹³C{¹H} NOE measurements, including long-range selective heteronuclear ¹³C{¹H} NOE enhancement measurements.

Scheme 3

The reaction of 1 with phenylhydrazine was investigated (Scheme 4) and the product was incorrectly characterized as 5-anilino-3,6-dimethyl-1-pyrazolo[4,3-*c*]pyridin-4-one (9, also called pyridinopyrazole) on the basis of elemental analysis, IR and mass spectral data²⁵. Probably, the authors were not aware of the earlier work of Stolle²¹ and Benary²² and did not even consider the isomeric structure 4 (bipyrazole). It was explained that hydrazone 2 underwent cyclization to the corresponding pyranopyrazole (3) as well as the hydrolysed to generate the starting materials (dehydroacetic acid and phenylhydrazine) (path a). Compound 3 on reaction with phenylhydrazine (generated *in situ* via path a) resulted in the formation of 9 (path b). The formation of pyridinopyrazole (9)^{25,26}. The structure revision was based on the isolation of the key intermediate 1-(5-hydroxy-3-methyl-1-phenylpyrazol-4-yl)-1,3-butanedione (10, also called 4-

Gelin *et al.*²⁷ in 1983 studied the reaction of 1 with phenylhydrazine and established as 4,5'-bipyrazole structure (4) instead of the previously reported pyridinopyrazole (9)^{25,26}. The structure revision was based on the isolation of the key intermediate 1-(5-hydroxy-3-methyl-1-phenylpyrazol-4-yl)-1,3-butanedione (10, also called 4-

Scheme 4

(acylacetyl)-1-phenyl-2-pyrazolin-5-one and its subsequent transformation to 3,6-dimethyl-1-phenylpyrazolo[2,3-c]pyrazol-4-(1*H*)-one (11) and 4 under different reaction conditions. The key intermediate 10 was obtained by refluxing 2 in acetic acid in good yields. This procedure did not in fact provide pyridinopyrazole (9) as erroneously claimed. Attempts to generate the product 10 without the isolation of 2 were unsuccessful.

Scheme 5

Singh *et al.*²⁸ working independently, reported the formation of some novel products in the reaction of 1 with 2-hydrazino-6-methoxy-4-methylquinoline (Scheme 6) in a separate communication. Quinolyhydrazone of 1 (12) underwent skeletal rearrangement to 1-[5-hydroxy-3-methyl-1-(6-methoxy-4-methyl-2-quinoly)pyrazol-4-yl]-

1,3-butanedione (13) which is analogous to compound 10. The mechanism proposed for its formation consists of a rearrangement of 12 involving a nitrogen nucleophilic attack at the C₂ lactone carbonyl with ring opening, thus generating 13. The mechanism was also supported by deuterium labeling studies experiments and ¹H NMR spectroscopy.

Scheme 6

A significant aspect of this work²⁸ was the treatment of 13 with 2-hydrazino-6-methoxy-4-methylquinoline under different reaction conditions (ethanol-hydrochloric acid or ethanol-sodium acetate-acetic acid), which resulted in the formation of either 4,5'-bipyrazole (14) (path a) or the product of C-C bond cleavage generating two molecules of 1-(6-methoxy-4-methyl-2-quinoly)-3-methylpyrazol-5-ol (15) (path b), respectively (Scheme 7). For the confirmation of structure of compound 15, it was prepared by the reaction of quinolyhydrazone (13) and ethyl acetoacetate. The physical data (m.p. 179–180 °C, TLC) and ¹H spectroscopic data [δ 2.3 (3H, s), 2.7 (3H, s), 3.9 (3H, s), 5.45 (1H, s), 7.0–8.0 (4H, m)]; C₁₅H₁₅O₂N₃, M⁺ 269 of 15 were in consonance with that obtained from C-C bond cleavage.

1-(5-Hydroxy-3-methyl-1-substitutedpyrazol-4-yl)-1,3-butanediones (10, 13 and 16 (Ar = 2-pyridyl)), a β -tricarbonyl system) were shown to exist in two predominant tautomeric forms A (keto/OH) and B (enol/OH) by a rigorous analysis of ¹H and ¹³C NMR spectral data^{27,29}. The diketo form on the side chain is favoured in (CH₃)₂SO-

Scheme 7

*d*₆ solution as compared to a CDCl₃ solution. On the other hand, O'Connell *et al.*²⁹ suggested that 10 exists as A on the basis of X-ray crystallography. Singh *et al.*³⁰ had studied the fragmentation behaviour of 10, 13 and 16

R = phenyl, 2-pyridyl, 2-quinoly

Scheme 8

using electron-impact mass spectrometry and the major process were interpreted. The common features were the loss of ketene, acetylonyl radical, acetone and two molecules of ketenes from the molecular ion (Scheme 8). All the processes were substantiated with the help of accurate mass measurements of the fragment ion and by a study of the 1st field-free region (FFR) metastable ions which were obtained by linked scans.

The reaction of 1-(5-hydroxy-3-methyl-1-substitutedpyrazol-4-yl)-1,3-butanediones (10, 13 and 16) were carried out with hydrazine, alkylhydrazines and arylhydrazines under different experimental conditions. It was found that the reaction leads to the formation of one compound 17 instead of a mixture of isomers (17, 18)³¹.

Although the reaction led to the formation of only one compound (17) and not to a mixture of isomers (17, 18), its structure assignment appeared to be a complex problem. This structure may present isomerism, tautomerism (OH/NH) and rotational isomerism (atropisomerism) thereby generating sixteen possible structures for discussion.

The structure, 17d (NH-Z), was eventually established by a combined use of X-ray crystallography, NMR (¹H and ¹³C) spectroscopy, AM1 calculations and the solid state cross polarisation magic angle spinning (CPMAS-NMR) spectrum of the compound³². The 4,5'-bipyrazole (4) crystallizes in the space group *P2*₁/*a* [C₂₀H₁₈N₄O, *a* = 11.801(2), *b* = 7.911(1), *c* = 18.363(2) Å, α = 90.00°, β = 100.04°, γ = 90.00°, *z* = 4]. The structure

corresponds to the NH-tautomer of the pyrazolinone moiety; the angle of twist corresponding to pyrazole rings, defined as $C_1-C_2-C_3-C_5$, is $-119.1(7)^\circ$. NMR spectrum allowed estimating the tautomeric equilibrium constant in solution and in solid state. Both the rotational barrier and the tautomerism are generally low, thus only average NMR signals are expected for a mixture of 17a-17c.

The ^{13}C CPMAS NMR spectrum also corresponds to NH tautomer of the pyrazolinone moiety as the chemical shifts of carbon atoms C3, C4 and C5 are at 150.3, 98.1 and 159.7. These values are in agreement with the values for NH tautomer in solution (CDCl_3): the chemical shifts of carbon atoms C3, C4 and C5 are at 146.8, 94.2 and 157.0. Full optimization of the geometries 17a-17d was carried out. In the case of 17d, the calculated geometry superposes well with the X-ray structure, the main difference being the nitrogen atom N_1 which is sp^2 according to the X-ray structure and sp^3 according to AM1 calculations. The three dihedral angle (in the order 1-phenyl/pyrazolinone, pyrazolinone/pyrazole, pyrazole/1'-phenyl) are: 17a 27.5, 91.2, 43.2° ; 17b 27.4, 79.8, 39.0° ; 17c 54.5, 85.2, 46.6° and 17d 54.1, 60.8, 41.9° [X-ray structure: 20.6, 60.9, 40.2°]. In OH tautomers, the OH group is early coplanar with the pyrazole ring: 17a 2.5° and 17b 7.3° . The corresponding heat of formation (in kcal mol^{-1}) and dipole moments (in D) are: 17a 159.84 (1.44), 17b 159.52 (1.75), 17c 160.44 (4.77) and 17d 161.22 (4.16). The combined use of NMR information (^1H and ^{13}C) and AM1 calculations pointed out to an equilibrium

between OH tautomer probably in the Z conformation and the NH tautomer probably in the E conformation. The structure of the type 17a, was also reported in the case of hydrazine itself ($R = \text{H}$)³³ and phenylhydrazine ($R = \text{C}_6\text{H}_5$)²⁷. Nevertheless, these two works lacked a convincing spectroscopic support. Surprisingly, Djerrari *et al.*³⁴ proposed structure 19a in solution (NMR) and 19c in gas phase (mass spectrometry).

It is noteworthy that in the ^1H NMR spectrum of 17 (Ar and R = phenyl, 4), the 3-methyl signal ($\sim\delta$ 1.791 ppm) was clearly shielded as compared to the one in simple pyrazolinones (~ 2.1 ppm). This shielding was assigned to the proximity of the 1'-phenyl ring which was confirmed by the NOE experiments as summarized below.

It was found that if 1'-phenyl ring is replaced by some other moiety such a signal of 3-methyl jumps to about δ 2.4 ppm which provided another proof that the methyl protons are shielded by the phenyl group. The fact that the signal at 1.791 ppm shows both NOE's with phenyl protons and H_4' , further indicated that 17 exists in two conformations³².

While treating 10/13/16 with a variety of hydrazines and employing different reaction conditions, an interest-

ing observation concerning the mechanism of formation bipyrazoles became known. Whereas all the hydrazines provided the expected bipyrazole on treatment with **10** in the presence of strong acid; unexpected formation of pyrazol-5-ols was observed with some hydrazines on performing the reaction in ethanol-acetic acid/sodium acetate (Scheme 9). The hydrazine attacked on the terminal carbonyl carbon of the side chain giving rise to the corresponding hydrazone (**20**) followed by ring closure to produce an intermediate. This intermediate then underwent (i) dehydration in the presence of strong acid yielding 4,5'-bipyrazole (**21**) and/or (ii) C-C bond cleavage resulting in the formation of pyrazol-5-ols (**22**, **23**) in ethanol-acetic acid/sodium acetate. Formation of pyrazol-5-ols (**22**, **23**) clearly indicated the cleavage of C-C bond in the proposed intermediate. The mechanism for these processes has been postulated in Scheme 9.

It was also observed that the above results depend on the nature of hydrazines employed. The available data (Table 1) indicate that electronic effects of bulky group in RNHNH₂ play a significant role in directing the course of the reaction³⁵. The conformational behaviour of 4,5'-bipyrazole is still under investigation using NMR spectroscopy and AM1 and PM3 calculations.

Scheme 9

Table 1. C-C bond cleavage; effect of R group in RNHNH₂

R	Cleavage
Phenyl,	No
<i>p</i> -nitrophenyl, pyridyl	
2,4-Dinitrophenyl,	Yes
2-benzothiazolyl,	
2-quinolyl	
2-Naphthyl	Yes

However, in a typical experiment when the reaction of **10** was performed in ethanol with 1-hydrazinophthalazine hydrochloride (**24**, a biologically important compound), there was formation of two products identified as 3-methyl-*s*-triazolo[3,4-*a*]phthalazine (**25**) and 4-acetyl-1-phenylpyrazol-5-ol (**26**) instead of the expected 4,5'-bipyrazole³⁶ (Scheme 10) based on elemental analysis, NMR (¹H and ¹³C) spectroscopy and mass spectrometry. The ¹H NMR spectrum of **26** displayed signals at δ 2.40 for both C₃-CH₃ and C₄-COCH₃ besides aromatic protons at δ 7.15–8.00 (5H). 4-Acetyl-1-phenylpyrazol-5-ol (**26**) type of compounds found applications in agrochemicals and extraction of metal ions³⁷ and can also be used for conversion to pyranopyrazole (**11**)³⁸. Moreover, reaction of **10** with hydroxylamine also generated pyrazolyloxazoles³⁹.

R = 4-Methyl-2-quinolyl, 2-pyridyl, 2-thiazolyl, phenyl

Scheme 10

With a view to extend the scope of this reaction, DHAA was converted to thiosemicarbazone **27** which on reaction with α -haloketones afforded the hydrazone (**28**) followed by its smooth conversion to 1-[5-hydroxy-3-methyl-1-(4-arylthiazol-2-yl)pyrazol-4-yl]-1,3-butanedione (**29**) (Scheme 11)⁴⁰. The reaction of **29** with various hydrazines generated 4,5'-bipyrazoles (**30**)⁴¹. The thiosemicarbazone **27**, was also found to form nickel(II) and palladium(II) chelates which were confirmed through spectroscopic techniques⁴².

Scheme 11

Synthesis and distinction between four isomeric pyranopyrazoles (**31-34**) and their pyridine analogues have been made by NMR (^1H and ^{13}C) spectroscopy. Complete analyses of the structural features of these compounds were achieved employing homonuclear $^1\text{H}\{^1\text{H}\}$ and two-bond heteronuclear $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ nuclear Overhauser effects techniques. The chemical shift of each carbon was confirmed by selective decoupling of the corresponding protons⁴³.

Conclusions

Presence of several electrophilic site in the molecule of dehydroacetic acid (3-acetyl-4-hydroxy-6-methyl-2H-pyran-2-one) makes it an attractive target for nucleophilic attack. In particular, reactions of DHAA with hydrazines provide useful synthesis involving rearrangements. These compounds undergo a wide variety of reactions leading to the formation of products, which display interesting structural features.

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References

1. K. Kakemi, T. Arita, M. Sezaki and T. Kiriya, *Yakuzaigaku*, 1958, **18**, 77.
2. Y. Kato, M. Sgrura and H. Yamada, *Gifu Yakka Daigaku Kiyo*, 1958, **8**, 37.
3. W. A. Sistrunk, *Food Technology*, 1957, **11**, 336.
4. S. Tanka, *Kolumin Eassei*, 1956, **11**, 138.
5. M. Z. Chalaca and J. D. Figueroa-Villar, *J. Mol. Struct.*, 2000, **554**, 225.
6. S. K. Talapatra, P. Lal, K. Biswas, A. Shaw, R. Chakrabarti and B Talapatra, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2001, **75**, 32.
7. S. Ohta, A. Tsujimura and M. Okamoto, *Chem. Pharm. Bull.*, 1981, **29**, 2762.
8. R. B. Gammill, T. M. Judge, G. Philips, Q. Zhang, C. G. Swell, B. V. Cheney, S. A. Mizsak, L. A. Dolak and E. P.

- Seest, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1994, **116**, 12113.
9. R. Bacardit, J. Cervello, P. de March, J. Marquet, M. Moreno-Manas and J. L. Roca, *J. Heterocyclic Chem.*, 1989, **26**, 1205.
 10. R. Bacardit and M. Moreno-Manas, *Chem. Lett.*, 1982, **5**.
 11. O. Prakash, A. Kumar, A. Sadana and S. P. Singh, *Synth. Commun.*, 2002, **32**, 2663.
 12. M. Fodili, M. Amari, B. Kolli, A. Robert, M. Baudy-Floc'h and P. Le Grel, *Synthesis*, 1999, **5**, 811.
 13. M. El-Abbassi, B. Djerrari, E. M. Essassi and J. Fifani, *Tetrahedron*, 1989, **30**, 7069.
 14. R. K. Kadian, I. Singh, B. S. Garg and R. P. Singh, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1983, **60**, 331.
 15. N. R. Rao and M. C. Ganorkar, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1988, **27**, 52 and references cited therein.
 16. S. G. Shirodhar, P. S. Mane and T. K. Chondhekar, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 2001, **40**, 1114.
 17. A. Strakovs, N. N. Tonkikh, M. Petrova, K. V. Ryzhanova and E. Palit, *Chem. Heterocycl. Compd. (Engl. Transl.)*, 2002, **38**, 449.
 18. B. C. Maiti and S. K. Maiti, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1998, **37**, 710.
 19. D. W. Emerson, R. L. Titus and R. M. Gonzalez, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1990, **55**, 3572.
 20. W. H. Perkin (Jr.) and C. Bernhart, *Ber.*, 1884, **17**, 1522.
 21. R. Stolle, *Ber.*, 1905, **38**, 3023.
 22. E. Benary, *Ber.*, 1910, **43**, 1070.
 23. A. A. Akherm, A. M. Moiseenkov, F. A. Lakhvich and S. P. Smul'skii, *Izv. Akad. Nauk SSSR, Ser. Khim.*, 1971, 1098 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1971, **75**, 76678).
 24. A. Cantos, P. de March, M. Moreno-Manas, A. Pla, F. Sanchez-Ferrando and A. Virgili, *Chem. Lett.*, 1986, 295; *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1987, **60**, 4425.
 25. V. K. Mahesh and R. S. Gupta, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1974, **12**, 570.
 26. M. A. Hassan, M. El-Kady and A. A. A. El-Mohay, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1982, **21**, 372.
 27. S. Gelin, B. Chantegrat, A. Nadi and A. Fruchier, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1983, **48**, 4078.
 28. S. P. Singh, O. Prakash and R. K. Vaid, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1984, **23**, 191.
 29. M. J. O'Connell, C. G. Ramsay and P. J. Steel, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1985, **38**, 401.
 30. S. P. Singh, R. K. Vaid, P. Dwakar and L. Singh, *Org. Mass. Spectrom.*, 1988, **23**, 10.
 31. J. Elguero, A. Martinez, S. P. Singh, M. Grover and L. S. Tarar, *J. Heterocyclic Chem.*, 1990, **27**, 865.
 32. D. Kumar, S. P. Singh, A. Martinez, A. Fruchier, J. Elguero, M. Martinez-Ripoll, J. S. Carrio and A. Virgili, *Tetrahedron*, 1995, **51**, 4891.
 33. S. Afridi, A. R. Katritzky and C. A. Ramsden, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin Trans. 1*, 1977, 1428.
 34. B. Djerrari, E. Essassi and J. Fifani, *Bull. Soc. Chim. Soc. (Fr.)*, 1991, 521.
 35. S. P. Singh, R. Naithani, R. Aggarwal and O. Prakash, *Synth. Commun.*, 2005, **35**, 611.
 36. S. P. Singh, D. Kumar and J. K. Kapoor, *Synth. Commun.*, 1994, **24**, 2645.
 37. H. Zimer and A. Amer, *Heterocycles*, 1987, **26**, 1177.
 38. M. A. Khan, G. P. Ellis and M. C. Pagotto, *J. Heterocycl. Chem.*, 2001, **38**, 193; *Heterocycles*, 1977, **6**, 983.
 39. A. Bendass, M. Hamdi and N. Sellier, *J. Heterocycl. Chem.*, 1999, **36**, 1291.
 40. S. P. Singh, L. S. Tarar and D. Kumar, *Synth. Commun.*, 1993, **23**, 1855.
 41. S. P. Singh, L. S. Tarar and D. Kumar, *Indian J. Heterocycl. Chem.*, 1993, **3**, 5.
 42. A. A. Kubaisi and K. Z. Ismail, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1994, **72**, 1785.
 43. D. Kumar, C. P. Kaushik and S. P. Singh, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1999, **38**, 1377.